

**THE PROBLEMS OF TRANSLATION OF MILITARY TERMS IN ENGLISH
AND UZBEK LANGUAGES (BASED ON THE INTERNET MEDIA)**

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The topicality of our article is in world linguistics the issues related to military terminology in a comparative aspect are being one of the controversial topics because of global economic and social relations. The problem stated in our article supports the facts in the deep study of the structures of word-building and semasiology of the terms in military discourse and the research conducted by the most famous scientists. In our opinion, the relevance of this study is also explained by the fact that it is necessary to study terms in this area as a way to reflect changes in linguistic culture, which is influenced by some important factors, namely globalization, computerization, informatization, etc. It becomes one of the most important issues in scientific research because it actually reflects the dynamics of social and spiritual life of Uzbek and English society. Taking into account all these facts, it can be summarized that the importance of translation activities and linguistic research of cultural transit of linguistic formations from one language to another is really growing in the world. The history of mankind has always been associated with wars. Military actions have not only catastrophic consequences, but are also a catalyst for powerful linguistic transformations.

The purpose of our article is to analyze military terms, identify them based on Internet sources and classify them in English.

The object of our article is to identify the basics of military terminology, to provide some examples according to the terms of military terminology and to support the concepts of scholars who worked in this field of study.

Many linguists and scientists of various fields have always pondered over the translation of military terms. Many of them contributed greatly to the development of this field and most of them have tried to establish books about the terminology of the military words. Scientists carried out a clarification of the terms and gave clear examples relying on the sources on the online media. Specifying the level of

scientific development, it should be noted that these issues have been actively investigated by many domestic and foreign authors. In particular, the works of K.Ya.Averbukh [1], M.N. Volodina [2], S.V. Grinev Grinevich [4], Dickson, Paul, and Ben Lando [8], and others. The specifics of the formation of English terminology are discussed in the works of S.N. Gorelikova [3], D.F. Kayumova, A.I. Shaidullina [5] and others. A comparative analysis of terminology (including military) in Uzbek and English is given in the works of M.A. Lazareva [6], Plekhov [7] and others.

It is obvious that translation of the military terms has a number of specific features that exist every language. However it characterizes a general sub language. Nevertheless, the military services of every country has its own peculiarities that correspond their own terminology. The basic importance of the practical and theoretical research into military terminology reflects that it can build an intercultural bridge between societies and countries. These kinds of factors makes exploring the translation of military terms crucial. We believe that English-language military terms, from the point of view of their interpretation, can be divided into the following groups:

a. Terms that are translated directly from English language to Uzbek language and it doesn't make any difficulty in interpreting them into the target language. Either English/ Uzbek or an international term is used as an equivalent, and in this case it can be called literal translation, for example, *chow hall - ovqatlanish zali*, *chemical weapon - kimyoviy qurol*, *military police - harbiy politsiya*, *field uniform - dala formasi*, *armed forces - qurolli kuchlar* [9].

b. Terms that exist in English lexicology but there is no equivalent in target language, generally accepted terminology can be used in this case. In order to achieve a relevant translation of such words, we can use modulation i.e. a method in which translators try to maintain naturalness by using various form the message done by changing the point of view. For example, *classified information - maxfiy ma'lumotlar*, *noncommissioned officers - kichik qo'mondon xodimlar*, *designated marksman - piyoda snayper* [9].

c. Terms which appear in source languages but it is hard to translate directly because of not having terminology that is accepted as general equivalent in Uzbek, for example, *cadence (The rhythmic step soldiers will all follow along to while marching) - kadentsiya (askarlar marshda yuradigan ritmik qadam)*. *Corporal (a noncommissioned officer ranking in the army above a private first class and below a sergeant and in the marine corps above a lance corporal and below a sergeant) - kapral (Armiyada oddiy va birinchitoifadan yuqori va serjantdandan past bo'lgan*

serjant). While translating these groups of terms into Uzbek, one can face some problems and we may use the following transformations in translation: transcription: *automatic pilot* (*samolyotni insonsiz avtomatik boshqaruv qurilmasi*) - *avtopilot*, *mine* - *mina*, *cook* - *kok* (*kema oshpazi*); partial or full transliteration: *se-condlieutenant* *ikkinchi leytenant* ; compensation method (giving definition for the given word): *payload raketa jangovar uskunalari* , *attack problem* - *tajovuzkor hujumning taktik vazifasi* [9], etc.

In conclusion, we can infer that translation of military terminology is playing an integral role in the world of interpretation as a subject that has its own norms and criteria. In fact, sometimes we find it difficult to find a correct equivalent according to the linguacultural variations in which makes it tough to find a suitable concordance without a deep analysis.

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